

Design and Characterization of a Self-Micro Emulsifying Drug Delivery System (SMEDDS) for the Delivery of Omega Fatty Acids

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The global market for nutraceuticals is expanding due to increased health awareness, yet the bioavailability of bioactive components, such as polyunsaturated fatty acids, is often compromised by low aqueous solubility and stability in the gastrointestinal tract. To overcome these limitations, Self-Micro Emulsifying Drug Delivery Systems (SMEDDS) have emerged as a vital strategy to enhance solubility and oral bioavailability. This study focuses on the design and characterization of a SMEDDS formulation specifically aimed at improving the delivery of omega fatty acids. **Methodology:** Surfactants and co-surfactants were screened via miscibility studies to determine optimal solubility. Pseudo-ternary phase diagrams were constructed using the aqueous titration method to identify the optimal ratios of oil, surfactant (Tween 80), and co-surfactant (PEG 400). The formulation was prepared using a high-shear homogenizer and characterized for self-emulsification time, viscosity, droplet size, zeta potential, in-vitro dissolution, and stability under accelerated conditions. **Results:** The miscibility study identified Tween 80 and PEG 400 as the ideal surfactant and co-surfactant, with a 2:1 ratio yielding the largest monophasic region on the phase diagram. The optimized SMEDDS exhibited a rapid self-emulsification time of less than one minute, a mean globule size of 645.2 nm, and a stable zeta potential of -34.9 mV. In-vitro dissolution studies demonstrated a drug release of over 63% in the first 15 minutes, significantly higher than that of pure oil. **Conclusion:** The developed SMEDDS formulation successfully improved the solubility and dissolution profile of omega fatty acids. The formulation remained physically stable for a month under various storage conditions, suggesting this approach is a viable strategy for delivering poorly water-soluble nutraceuticals.

Keywords: Nutraceutical formulation, SMEDDS, Fatty acids, Solubility

INTRODUCTION

The growing awareness among people to live healthy lives has led to a significant increase in the global market for nutraceuticals in recent years. Additionally, there is a significant desire among some segments of the general public to use nutraceuticals to augment daily nutritional needs in order to prevent chronic diseases associated with deficiencies (1). The term "nutraceutical" refers to a food or element of food which offers health or clinical advantages, such as illness prevention or therapy. Products like nutritional supplements, isolated nutrients, herbal products, genetically modified designer foods, processed and functional foods, etc. are all included

in this description (2). A formulator may find it simple to create a pharmaceutical formulation that contains bioactive food, but achieving a good bioavailability for these nutraceuticals can be very difficult. Low solubility, stability, and/or permeability of the bioactive component in the GIT frequently compromise the bioavailability (3). One of the nutrients with exceptional nutraceutical potential is polyunsaturated fatty acids. Numerous metabolites of polyunsaturated fatty acids, particularly essential fatty acids and eicosanoids derived from arachidonic acid or eicosatetraenoic acid, actively contribute to the nutraceutical qualities associated with polyunsaturated fatty acids. Through several biochemical pathways, including antioxidant and

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anti-inflammatory properties, polyunsaturated fatty acids have nutraceutical functions in diseases like cancer, fatty liver condition, cardiovascular disorders, type II diabetes, and neurodegeneration (4). It has been discovered that the majority of novel and natural chemical entities, including fatty acids, are poorly soluble in water. Formulation scientists must solve the problem of poor aqueous solubility in order to deliver such medications more effectively. Simple oily solutions, micellar solutions, microemulsions, nanoemulsions, and more recently, SMEDDS, are the best examples (5). The SMEDDS has several advantages over traditional emulsion, including ease of manufacture, scalability, and robust physical stability (6).

SMEDDS are isotropic oil and surfactant combinations that, when added to water and gently swirled, produce oil-in-water microemulsions (7). The SMEDDS has globule sizes ranging from 50 to 250 nm (8). It has been demonstrated that their self-dispersion tendency and small droplet sizes upon dispersion enhance the absorption of drugs from the wide interfacial region. This formulation has received a lot of interest lately because it is simple to create (9), has a higher drug loading capacity (10), and reduces the food effect (11). SMEDDS can drastically lower the dose volume in comparison to microemulsions and nanoemulsions, which leads to appealing business sustainability and patient compliance. Usually, a water-free approach reduces the dose volume, improves medication stability, and has less solvent effects (12).

Fig. 1: Advantages of SMEDDS

The key objective of current research was to improve the solubility and oral bioavailability of omega fatty acids through SMEDDS. The formulated SMEDDS was assessed for its morphology, self-emulsification performance, in-vitro dissolution, and stability tests. The findings of this study will assist in designing lipid-based formulations for other nutraceuticals that are poorly soluble in water.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

The fatty acid rich oil was obtained from Research-Lab Fine Chem Industries, Mumbai. Cremophor RH 40, Polyethylene Glycol 400, Tween 20 and Tween 80 were procured from Himedia Laboratories. Span 20 and Span 60 were obtained from Molychem Industries. All the chemicals and solvents used in the

research were of analytical quality and were used without further purification.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Miscibility Study

The different surfactants were screened by homogenizing them with an excess quantity of fatty acid using a high-shear homogenizer at 3000 rpm while maintaining the temperature at 35°C. To this mixture phosphate buffer was added to mimic the ionic composition and pH of intestinal fluid (13). The vortexing was continued to make the oil phase miscible with the aqueous phase. After attaining equilibrium, the mixtures were given a centrifuge for 10 minutes at 1000 rpm. The supernatant was then removed using a glass pipette for visual examination, and the concentration of ALA

was determined using a UV-visible double beam spectrophotometer. (Shimadzu UV-1800) at 230 nm. (14) (6)

2.2.2. Construction of pseudo-ternary phase diagram

Based on miscibility study, the pseudo-ternary phase diagram was constructed for fatty acid as oil component, selected mixture of surfactant and co-surfactant (Smix). Water, oil and Smix in specific ratio (1:1, 2:1, 1:2) were the three variables utilized. The aqueous titration method was used to create the ternary phase diagram (15,16). To create the phase diagram, a gradual titration with distilled water was performed to each weight fraction of oil and Smix by increasing the proportion of oil by 10% up to 90%. The production of a transparent and easily flowable o/w micro emulsion was then visually seen. A pseudo-ternary phase diagram was used to depict the physical condition of the micro emulsion. The aqueous phase was represented by one axis, the oil phase by another, and the Smix at different weight ratios (1:1, 2:1, 1:2) by a third. The transition of the sample's appearance from transparent to turbid was used to identify the phase boundary. The online software ternary plot was used to create the phase diagram. Ternary phase diagrams were also created for different surfactant to co-surfactant ratios, such as 1:2 and 2:1 (17) (6).

2.2.3. Preparation of SMEDDS

The SMEDDS were prepared using a Smix ratio based on pseudo-ternary phase diagrams. The fatty acid was used as oil phase and the selected amount of Smix was mixed with the oil phase slowly while stirring continuously using high shear homogenizer until a uniform mixture was obtained (18). To ensure complete mixing, this mixture was heated to 40°C in a water bath for 10 minutes while being stirred occasionally (6). After being examined for turbidity, phase separation, or gelling impact, this formulation concentrate was stored at room temperature for further analysis.

2.2.4. Evaluation of SMEDDS

- Self-emulsification time and visual evaluation

Using distilled water as an aqueous medium at $37\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and magnetic stirrer running at 200 rpm were used to test the self-emulsification capability. 1 ml SMEDDS formulation was added to 100 ml of distilled water, and the time required between the SMEDDS addition and completion of emulsification process was noted. The emulsification process was visually examined (19).

- Viscosity

Viscosity of the prepared SMEDDS was determined by using rotating spindle Brookfield viscometer (20). After weighing, 20 g of concentrate was added in to a beaker. Viscosity was determined with the help of spindle no. 6 and speed of 12 rpm at 25°C for 5 min. Viscosity measurement was done in triplicate.

- Droplet size

The measurement of emulsion droplet size was achieved by Particle Size Analyzer- Litesizer DLS 500 (Anton Paar) with the dynamic light scattering at 25°C . Using a magnetic stirrer, 100 μL of SMEDDS was mixed with 100 mL of distilled water with gentle stirring. To settle the undissolved fraction, beakers were incubated at 25°C for 30 minutes. All investigations were conducted three times, and the z-average diameter values were utilized. The polydispersity index (PDI) and % transmittance was also determined in the same procedure. (21)

- Zeta potential

The magnitude of surface charge has a direct correlation with emulsion stability. Using a Litesizer DLS 500 (Anton Paar), the zeta potential of the diluted SMEDDS formulation was determined. The SMEDDS are diluted 20 times with distilled water and stirred for a minute using magnetic stirrer.

- *In-vitro* dissolution

The Paddle type (USP type II) dissolution apparatus was used to conduct an *in-vitro* drug release study. Fatty acid-containing SEMDDDS was put into hard gelatin capsules ("size 00") and added to pH 6.8 phosphate buffer, which is perpetuated at $37\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The paddle's revolution speed was maintained at 50 revolutions per minute. At 5, 10, 15, 30, 45, and 60

minutes, the 5 mL aliquot was taken out and passed via membrane filters with 0.45 μm pores. To maintain the sink condition, the dissolving medium aliquot was replaced. The concentration of ALA was determined spectrophotometrically at 230 nm. (6)

- Stability study

As a part of stability analysis conducted in compliance with ICH guidelines to evaluate the effects of humidity and temperature on the SMEDDS, prepared SMEDDS was held for a month at room temperature (RT) and under accelerated circumstances ($40^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $75\% \pm 5\% \text{RH}$). To confirm the stability of the produced formulation during the storage phase, parameters including emulsification efficiency,

physical appearance, globule size and percent transmittance were evaluated. (17)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Miscibility Study

When added to the aqueous phase at suitable temperature, self-emulsifying formulation made of surfactant, co-surfactant and oil should be a transparent, single phase liquid with a high solvent capacity. (22) The miscibility of fatty acids with aqueous phase in the presence of various surfactants was evaluated visually and the concentration of ALA in each mixture was noted using spectrophotometer. The results were mentioned in the table 1:

Table 1: Miscibility Study

Sr. No.	Surfactant	Visibility	ALA concentration
1	Cremophor RH 40	Clear	248.63 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
2	PEG 400	Clear	344.26 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
3	Span 20	Turbid	45.29 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
4	Span 60	Hazy	158.49 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
5	Tween 20	Hazy	106.06 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
6	Tween 80	Clear	438.389 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

On visual inspection the Cremophor RH 40, PEG 400 and Tween 80 showed a clear emulsion. Thus, Tween 80 and PEG 400 were chosen as surfactant and co-surfactant respectively considering the ALA concentration.

3.2. Pseudo-ternary phase diagram

SMEDDS formulation should be simple and safe, prepared using nontoxic surfactants (23). The key to achieving balance during loading and avoiding phase separation when diluted in GIT fluids is figuring out the excipient ratio for SMEDDS. In order to determine the link between the SMEDDS components, a phase diagram study was carried out (17).

The pseudo ternary phase diagram was plotted for three variables i.e. water, oil and Smix in specific ratio (1:1, 2:1, 1:2) shown in fig 2. The Smix ratio of 2:1 shows the higher monophasic region. Because Tween 80 lowers interfacial tension and allows surfactants to penetrate into the aqueous phase, small globules were generated at high concentrations. Additionally, a flexible film was created by PEG 400 which raises the system's entropy. It also modifies the viscosity, polarity, refractive index and density of the aqueous phase, further reduced interfacial tension. Therefore, the 2:1 Smix ratio was chosen for additional investigation.

Fig. 2: Pseudo-ternary phase diagrams (a) Smix 1:1 (b) Smix 2:1 (c) Smix 1:2

3.3. Characterization of SMEDDS

The SMEDDS was prepared utilizing a high shear homogenizer according to the miscibility test and pseudo ternary phase diagram. The prepared SMEDDS was stored in a tightly closed container for further evaluation.

- Self-emulsification time and visual evaluation

Visual assessment was used to evaluate self-emulsification. Under the defined conditions, the time required for complete emulsification of the SMEDDS was found to be less than a minute. The clear, isotropic, fine solution indicates the formation of a microemulsion (24).

- Viscosity

The viscosity character has been evaluated to make sure SMEDDS is physically stable. Additionally, the more viscous formulations can impact drug release and its bioavailability due to low emulsification rate. Thus, SMEDDS dispersion in an aqueous medium is crucial (25). The viscosity of the formulation was found to be 64.6 ± 2.4 cP, that is low enough to assist rapid emulsification.

- Droplet size and zeta potential

The prepared SMEDDS had a mean globule size of 645.2 nm and a PDI of 0.861 (Fig. 3). The adsorbed surfactant layer and the observed zeta potential of -34.9 mV (Fig. 4) provide the repulsion needed to stop globular coalescence. This outcome validates SMEDDS's physical stability.

Fig. 3: Mean globule size of SMEDDS

Fig. 4: Zeta potential of SMEDDS

- In vitro dissolution studies

Since a drug dissolve as a free molecule, micelle, or microemulsion droplet upon contact with water, conventional in-vitro dissolution techniques are inadequate for studying the in-vitro dissolution of SMEDDS (26). Consistent release kinetics are ensured by dissolution studies utilizing hard gelatin capsules. The release of fatty acid from SMEDDS was studied in a phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) as a dissolving medium (Fig. 5). The first 15 minutes showed a greater drug release (63.19%). When SMEDDS formulations are added to dissolution media and gently stirred, the fatty acids in the oil phase of the SMEDDS may cause immediate emulsification into the water. When compared to the pure oil contained in the hard gelatin capsule, the fatty acid release from SMEDDS was significantly higher.

Fig. 5: In-vitro drug release profile

- Stability study

The outcomes of stability study parameters are shown in Table. The self-emulsification time, visual assessment, drug content assay, transmittance percentage, and globule size of SMEDDS formulation were examined. SMEDDS did not exhibit any cloudiness or precipitation during storage. After dilution, the microemulsion system showed a consistent globule size distribution. Self-emulsification duration, percentage transmittance, and globule size all exhibit negligible variations. As a result, it was concluded that the SMEDDS was stable under both room temperature and accelerated circumstances ($40\pm 2^\circ\text{C}/75\pm 5\%\text{RH}$).

Table 2: Stability study parameters

Condition	Parameters	0 th Day	30 th Day
At room temperature	Visual inspection	Clear	Clear
	Self-emulsification time	48 sec	52 sec
	Drug content	95.6 %	92.2 %
	% Transmittance	89.6 %	88.5 %
	Droplet size	645.2 nm	715.8 nm
Accelerated condition	Visual inspection	Clear	Clear
	Self-emulsification time	48 sec	55 sec
	Drug content	95.6 %	89.2 %
	% Transmittance	89.6 %	92.0 %
	Droplet size	645.2 nm	749.1 nm

CONCLUSION

This study successfully developed a Self-Micro Emulsifying Drug Delivery System (SMEDDS) for omega fatty acids, addressing the critical challenge of poor water solubility often found in nutraceuticals. By utilizing a specific mixture of Tween 80 and PEG 400, the researchers achieved a stable, isotropic formulation that rapidly emulsifies in water with a small droplet size (645.2 nm), which is essential for enhancing absorption.

The study confirmed that SMEDDS significantly outperforms pure oily solutions in terms of drug release rates, offering a more effective delivery method for bioactive fatty acids. Furthermore, stability tests confirmed the formulation's robustness over a month, indicating its potential for commercial scalability and use in the nutraceutical industry to treat

conditions like cardiovascular disorders and neurodegeneration.

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